

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS AND DIFFERENT ASPECTS BETWEEN TOURIST SERVICES AND TOURIST PRODUCTS

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Abstract: This article describes the specific features and differences between tourist services and tourist products. In recent years, in our country, the impact on the development of services, in particular, the conditions of tourist hotels and catering services, has been highlighted.

Keywords: tourism service, the final form of expression, the process of creation, satisfying the needs of the consumer, creating a tourist product

The research conducted abroad on the regulation of tourism services mainly originates from market economy research under the economic paradigm and has formed different schools and views. In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, a special emphasis is placed on the development of the service sector, including the development of roadside services, such as household and catering services, which are highly needed by tourists in the centers of cities and districts, as part of the 34th goal. It is also planned to introduce special programs to improve the living conditions of tourists, to improve the mechanisms for the development of catering services in the republic, to provide comprehensive support to the activities of service entities in the field, and to provide them with additional benefits.

Based on the analysis in the research, generalization of the modern terminology of the theory of tourism, and current approaches to determining the nature of different definitions of tourism, we formed the author's views of the concept in this study, according to which the tourism sector is an object of market relations, the need for which is during a tourist trip, travel and preparation for it it allows to meet the demand in the characteristic, similar, etc. entities of the tourist services market. Based on the summarization of literature sources and the practice of tourism enterprises, in order to deeply differentiate the concepts of tourist service and tourist product, we identified a number of classification signs in the research. We have summarized their characteristic differences in the table below. (Table 1).

Table 1.

Specific characteristics and differences between tourism services and tourism products

Sign	Tourist and others.	Tourist product
Place of purchase and consumption	It can be consumed mainly in the place of production	It can be bought anywhere, but it can be consumed only at the place of production of tourist services.
According to the final form of the expression	Direct use is the naming of the product, the use of its consumer qualities	Product
On the subject of formation and implementation	Creation and implementation is carried out by all entities of the tourist infrastructure. Implementation can be done by both producers and manufacturers tourism entities	The exclusive right of the tourist operator to form a complex tourist product. Implementation can be done both by tour operators and by tour operators agents.
The process of creation	Converting a natural and recreational resource into a tourist service	A combination of tourist services
Services by the number of subjects involved in the creation of the product	This is mainly the result of the production activity of one tourism infrastructure enterprise	The result of the production activity of many enterprises
To meet the needs of the consumer	It is designed to meet the specific needs of the tourist	Designed to meet the complex needs of the tourist

A critical analysis and generalization of the current approaches to the typology of tourist services and the study of the practical aspects of their presentation allow us to propose an extended classification of them based on the grouping of the following characteristics, and we can see the following:

- ❖ intensity of demand,
- ❖ tourist consumption volume,
- ❖ introduction of tourist services.
- ❖ innovation,
- ❖ participation in the creation of a tourist product,
- ❖ economic fundamentals,
- ❖ geographical features,
- ❖ types of tourist markets,
- ❖ attitudes towards tourist consumption,
- ❖ term,
- ❖ place of purchase and consumption,
- ❖ materiality,
- ❖ source of funding,
- ❖ consumption character,
- ❖ the nature of the demand.

In recent years, in our country, special attention has been paid to the development of services, in particular, tourist hotel conditions and catering services. As a result of the above

researches, we have depicted the following image in order to optimize the development of tourism in the region: Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Theoretical optimal mechanism of development of the regional economy¹

In regional tourism, catering services are a real reality that has developed on the basis of the centuries-old experience of our people, the rise of cultural and spiritual character, and has become an integral part of the life of tourists. This reality is also reflected in the description of this field by scientists. Usually, tourist accommodations and catering services are referred to as a general name of the economic sector, but in fact, this sector is composed of independent sectors that complement each other and have special characteristics. The reason for this is the great importance of this sector in improving the efficiency of the reforms carried out to ensure economic stability by improving the optimal regulatory mechanisms for the development of tourism in the region, improving the living conditions of tourists, forming modern rural and urban infrastructure.

In the application of this mechanism, the main principles of the regulation of the tourism sector today are the development of a strategy for the development of regional tourism. Identifying strategic long-term goals and short-term objectives. Establishing organizations responsible for tourism development (eg national or regional tourism agencies) and structures will pool the necessary resources to implement a common tourism development strategy that coordinates among various stakeholders. Development of marketing strategies and promotion campaigns to increase the tourism attractiveness of the region and attract potential tourists in the organization of infrastructure (e.g. transport, hotels, restaurants and other tourist facilities) and basic services (e.g. information services,

¹Developed by the author based on scientific sources

travel agencies) necessary for the development of tourism necessary. The use of the Internet and social networks is important in these processes. The region ensures the processes of active involvement of the local community in the process of tourism development, taking into account their interests and employment of the local population in the tourism sector. In order to minimize the impact of tourism and preserve natural and cultural resources, it is necessary to introduce the principles of sustainable tourism.

In order to develop and improve the legal documents necessary for the regulation and development of the tourism industry, to introduce mechanisms to control the quality of services provided to tourists and to maintain high standards, organizational aspects are necessary for the successful development of tourism in the region and to maximize the economic and social benefits from it. Grounding processes will be a great support for the development of tourism in the region. In recent years, the research of socio-economic processes with the help of models is becoming more important. The most widely used models in the development of economic sectors can be divided into three types according to the purpose of construction, scope of application and effectiveness.

❖ **Type 1** classical models that are applied in wide areas of development, have the characteristic of unification in the development of models for determining the reaction to new directions of the development of the field, and structurally express the connected, branched properties of social elements;

❖ **2nd round** developing models that structurally and parametrically represent a new view of a whole system, or its independent system, oriented to a specific object;

❖ **3rd round** Quantitative models that determine the reaction of the system to input variables and provide scientific justification of reality, participating as a mechanism for realizing the main goal of development or as a part of it.

To conclude, in the theoretical justification of the development of the field of tourist accommodation and general catering services, the models of this tourist mechanism acquire the characteristics of development, and the use of the 1st type models in the theory of the development of the field is very different. The main reason for this is that the network of tourist accommodation and general catering services takes place in social reality and is directly related to the inner psyche of a person.

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